

Autonomous collaborative mobile robot for greenhouses: Design, development, and validation tests

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a mobile agricultural robot capable of performing high-capacity transport tasks within greenhouses in presence of people or other agricultural machines. The main objective is to provide the robot with enough technology to work collaboratively with nearby human workers. In addition, the robot must also be able to transport 100 kilograms in a safe way over uneven terrain, a characteristic not usually found in existing greenhouse robots. This is important to ensure the sustainability of intensive greenhouse cultivation, as it is essential to allow more flexible use of robots when adapting. This would allow for expanding infrastructure size and operating volume to suit different greenhouse conditions, thus maximising production. The robot is fitted with different sensors to enable autonomous navigation, perception, and to identify the environment and the operators (3D LiDAR, stereo cameras, and ultrasound). It also features the hardware necessary for cloud connection to share data in real time. All sensors have been validated to work correctly, hence the robot can move around the greenhouse. With the software currently used for collaborative robotics, the ultrasounds correctly identify the environment, and cameras and LiDAR can locate the farmer correctly. In this work, several gaps in greenhouse robotics are addressed by designing, developing, and validating a collaborative mobile robot with advanced sensors and algorithms with IoT integration. The robot lays the foundation for the implementation of autonomous navigation, collaborating with farmers in real-time and efficient operation in complex greenhouse environments, laying the groundwork for future advances in agricultural automation.

1. Introduction

In recent years, many researchers have focused on analyzing the importance of greenhouses, speculating on the results and significance of the state of the land and demand in the next 20 to 30 years (Nemali, 2022; Durmanov et al., 2023). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) anticipates that by 2050, demand will increase by 70% due to overpopulation and the demand for food for humans and animals (FAO, 2024). Based on these data, achieving efficient and sustainable agricultural production in an increasingly urbanized environment is essential, considering the decrease in arable land and increased labour costs (Gogoi et al., 2020). In this scenario, plastic-intensive crop production has become the best alternative, which, following the COVID-19 pandemic, has highlighted the importance of safety in the agro-food sector (Fairbairn and Guthman, 2020). Greenhouses cover an area of 496.800 hectares globally, with 42.7% of them located on the Mediterranean coast (Hick, 2019). Although robotic harvesting has been successful in large-scale crops, limitations arise in other areas of agriculture. Factors such as the cost of investment and the need for specialized knowledge to maintain and operate the robots may hinder smallholder farmers' adoption of this technology. It is also essential to consider the potential impact on employment in the sector, as robotics could move human workers. However, despite these difficulties, agriculture is adopting more advanced technology that improves production, allowing a shift from small to large farms with less labour. The use

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of this technology is crucial, and currently automation and agricultural robotics techniques focused on machine-to-machine communication and, more importantly, machine-to-human interaction are being applied (Britannica, 2022). The development of robotic technologies for agriculture is expected to increase considerably in the next 30 years, as it is an active area of research and innovation (Khan et al., 2021). Despite existing challenges, such as customizing robotics for diverse climatic and topographical conditions, it is imminent as the world tends toward robotization, which, through human interaction, will combine strength and precision to develop efficiently operated greenhouses.

To make greenhouses the most viable solution, the adoption of technology must be an essential part of this process, particularly the automation and robotisation of the various procedures involved in vegetable production. This encompasses the entire process from transplanting to transporting the product to destination markets, including the stages of harvesting and post-harvesting autonomously. However, the delicate nature of the environment poses challenges for robots in greenhouses, as they operate within a more complex system than robots in industrial or agricultural settings. These robots are affected not only by the characteristics of crops (such as colour, size, shapes, textures, and variable locations) but also by environmental factors (such as lighting, positioning of fruits, branches, and leaves, monitoring of the health of the crop lifecycle and cutting of the soil) and, in addition, by elements and people in constant motion (Rodríguez et al., 2013). Moreover, for a mobile robot to navigate diverse environments and effectively accommodate crop variability, it is essential to implement localization techniques (Bac et al., 2013; Ko et al., 2014), which require exhaustive adaptation of sensors to this environment. Consequently, numerous research institutions are dedicated to improving the detection capabilities of the robot through technologies such as cameras, radio frequency identification (RFID), and magnetic systems, refining the robot's design for better adaptation to its surroundings, among others (Montoya-Cavero et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2016). However, this task is complicated by the fact that, as is well known, navigation using elements such as a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) or a Global Positioning System (GPS) does not work well indoors (Mousazadeh, 2013), especially within greenhouses, where crops are very close together and continue to grow (Aguiar et al., 2020). This becomes one of the main problems of this type of application and, consequently, one of the main objectives of current research in greenhouses. This challenging task can be considerably improved by applying high-level techniques that use local sensors, comparing internal models to correct the trajectory (Epstein et al., 2017), a concept currently known as a "digital twin". In order to maximize production, there is increasing emphasis on the use of cooperative techniques that allow robots to work with the environment. These techniques, for example, can help robot self-localization (Feng et al., 2020). A powerful application is when these techniques are used to collaborate with humans or farmers, which means a close human-robot collaboration that aligns with "Collaborative Robotics". Equipping agricultural robots with sensors that allow them to observe and listen to the farmer and then act accordingly is a significant advance in robotics, considerably increasing the complexity of robot design (Vicentini, 2021). Combining Internet connectivity allows robots to cooperate with other machines or elements installed in the greenhouse, further maximizing productivity (Lytridis et al., 2021). In this case, components that offer wireless connection to a server must be added to connect the robot to the Internet of Things (IoT). In addition to managing the large amount of data collected by the sensors (Big Data management), it allows implementing "cooperative robotics" algorithms, one of the main objectives of the project funding this work (Lins and Givigi, 2021).

Agriculture robots for planting, transplanting, pollinating, applying plant protection products, transporting materials, and harvesting tasks require specific technology to perform autonomous navigation in greenhouses (Rodríguez et al., 2013). However, only some prototypes have sensors and algorithms that allow one to establish collaboration between robots and humans. They have environmental perception sensors for navigation, ranging from LiDAR for mapping to RGB-D (red, green, blue, and depth) cameras that can detect and identify objects with their depth. With the help of laser technology, (Abanay et al., 2022) presented a Robot Operating Systems (ROS) based navigation method with a 2D LiDAR on the "AgriEco" robot inside a raspberry greenhouse, carrying out the transport of objects. In (Choudhary et al., 2021), a similar work is presented in which Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) is performed with a LiDAR and a RGB-D camera in a narrow greenhouse with a tomato crop to transport vegetable crates. Regarding related data, (Cañadas-Aránega et al., 2024) presents a greenhouse model and a greenhouse mapping dataset with a novel SLAM technique with two LiDARs, whose data, from a tomato plantation, were recorded for two months. This information helps to optimise the application of plant protection products by coordinating the robot's speed and spray rate (Sanchez-Hermosilla et al., 2010; Sánchez-Hermosilla et al., 2013). Although many works are related to robotics in greenhouses (Sánchez-Molina et al., 2024), few carry out collaborative control for robots. In (Zhong et al., 2013), collaborative telerobotics techniques are applied inside a greenhouse to monitor the life cycle of plants in collaboration with farmers. Subsequently, in (Zhong et al., 2015), different planning techniques used

in greenhouses with robots are described to obtain higher agricultural yields, considering the flow of local farmers in the environment. In (Dusadeerungsikul and Nof, 2019), different collaborative control techniques are applied in greenhouses on a differential mobile robot in simulation, in which objects emulating people are placed. In this case, it is observed how existing works perform mathematical applications or simulations in greenhouses, but none of them is applied in a real environment. To date, work with collaborative robots in greenhouses has been based only on simulated systems or basic tasks without implementing novel techniques. This work focuses on validating the design and sensors needed for collaborative work.

In this way, the main gaps observed in the literature according to the above review are the following ones:

- Collaborative robotics in real greenhouse environments: Although previous research has mainly focused on simulations or theoretical models, this paper fills this gap by developing and testing a collaborative mobile robot in a real greenhouse environment. This work addresses the challenge of human-robot interaction using cameras (a monocular one from Orbbec and a stereo one from Bumblebee) and currently employed algorithms (ORB_SLAM, MoveNet, and MOLA), allowing robots to work together with farmers in dynamic and complex environments such as Mediterranean greenhouses. To achieve this, mechanical design is a trivial step, placing each sensor in place to ensure its correct functioning. Each of these algorithms can identify the operator in its full range of vision, which is a fundamental step in ensuring the safety and integrity of the system. This practical application of collaborative robotics significantly advances previous work but needs real-world validation.
- Challenges of robotic navigation and adaptation to greenhouse conditions: Greenhouse environments present unique challenges for autonomous navigation, such as the inefficiency of GPS/GNSS systems and the need for robots to adapt to diverse conditions, such as dense crops, variable lighting, and complex topography. This paper addresses this shortcoming by thoroughly testing current algorithms used for navigation, such as vision-based systems and SLAM algorithms with cameras (two cameras, Orbbec and Bumblebee) and LiDAR (Velodyne VLP16), and validating them in a real greenhouse, placing them under rigorous mechanical design in locations where maximum efficiency is obtained. This helps solve the critical problem of indoor navigation and adapts robotics to the specific environmental requirements of greenhouses.
- IoT integration and Big Data management to improve agricultural efficiency: The paper addresses the gap related to IoT integration and data-driven agriculture by equipping the robot with the ability to connect to IoT systems. The onboard PC has a wireless connection card with 802.11ax connections, which, together with long-range antennas, can pick up WIFI waves to 10 meters. This will enable real-time monitoring, data management, and interaction with other machines, increasing the potential for more efficient and automated greenhouse operations. IoT integration is essential in agriculture, where machines can operate collaboratively and autonomously, maximizing productivity due to real-time data exchange and improved decision-making.
- Real-world testing and validation of robotic systems: Many studies on greenhouse robotics have remained theoretical or based on simulations. This paper fills this gap by validating the robot design and navigation systems through real-world testing with farmers. For this purpose, the robot was taken to the IFAPA greenhouse at the AGROCONNECT facility, where it was fully completed and tested. All sensor locations were validated with the farmer, and the different algorithms were used. This practical approach ensures the technology is feasible and effective in real agricultural environments, providing a fundamental basis for future developments and improvements.

In general, this work contributes extensively by addressing critical gaps in greenhouse robotics, from the development of collaborative robots in real-world environments to the approach to solving technical challenges related to navigation, IoT integration, and adaptation for various farming environments. It lays the foundation for future innovations in autonomous and collaborative farming, especially in complex environments such as Mediterranean greenhouses, and establishes a solid basis for real-world testing and further technological development.

The rest of the document is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the specifications that have been taken into account for the design of the collaborative robot. Section 3 comment the design stage of the robot, focusing on the electronic, electrical, and mechanical aspects. Section 4 discusses the actual test sites where the tests were performed. Section 5 shows the validated results of both the real robot and the sensors from a collaborative robotics point of view. Finally, section 6 presents the conclusions and future work.

2. Design specifications

In this section, the specifications and security restrictions from the current standards for the robot design are described. In order to achieve a collaborative agricultural robot able to cooperate with other robots in a greenhouse, the main objectives and the standards to be followed for the design are:

- Construction of a medium-sized platform with a high degree of maneuverability. To achieve this, the design must comply with the main safety standards for agricultural robotics, particularly emphasizing the principles of highly automated machine design (ISO 18497:2018) and their control (ISO 11783:2001). Furthermore, it is necessary to consider the technical guide from the National Institute for Safety and Hygiene at Work (INSHT) on manual handling of loads, which defines the most important guidelines that any operator must consider for weight manipulation. More specifically, the robot must adhere to the basic non-industrial robot standards (ISO 13482:2014), with a focus on mobile robotics application (ISO 23482-2:2019), as well as safety requirements for industrial mobile robots (ANSI/RIA R15.05-1:2020).
- Considering all the safety standards mentioned in the previous paragraph, one of the most critical requirements revolves around the robot's speed. It must be able to move at approximately 0.5 m/s (ISO 18497:2018), thereby ensuring both its own integrity and the safety of the surrounding environment.
- The transporting is the main task to be performed by the robot, assisting the farmers while they are harvesting. It must be capable of carrying a maximum payload of 100 kg through the greenhouse, ensuring stability even at maximum weight, as indicated in the ISO 18497:2018 standard.
- The robot must be able to navigate in outdoor, so that it is able to move for example between different greenhouses.
- It must be able to navigate autonomously within a typical plastic Mediterranean greenhouse, which accounts for 92% of the total greenhouse area worldwide (estimated at around $500,000\text{ ha}$ (Rijswick, 2018; Hick, 2019)). To this end, it must be equipped with sensors oriented towards the recognition of objects, other robots, and farmers working alongside it, validating the correct functioning of each sensor with the most common algorithms currently in use.
- It must be able to work in a collaborative way with the farmer and in a cooperative way with other robots.
- The robot must be able to connect to the cloud.
- It should be an energetically efficient robot, considering the possibility of meeting its energy needs with renewable sources. This is essential to ensure sustainability in greenhouse interior transportation.

2.1. Mechanic design specifications

The robot must be able to transport as many crates as possible throughout the greenhouse to save as many trips as possible between the point of origin and the destination. This poses a new challenge: to facilitate efficient transport by the operator and to achieve a balance between size and maneuverability in the middle of the crops while saving as much energy as possible.

On the one hand, from a design point of view, the ISO 13698-1:2003 and ISO 5687:2018 standards, which define the European pallet at $1200 \times 800\text{ mm}$ for the storage of fruits and vegetables, used by local farmers in the region, aligning their infrastructure and daily operations with this standard, ensure a uniform national transport system. Furthermore, by European Regulation No. 543/2011, which standardizes and advises on the preservation of various vegetables, the dimensions of a box of aubergine, zucchini, and cucumber are defined as $0.50 \times 0.37 \times 0.26\text{ m}$, while peppers have dimensions of $0.60 \times 0.40 \times 0.32\text{ m}$. The platform base must be able to carry at least two boxes of peppers, representing the most unfavorable scenario in terms of size.

On the other hand, from the point of view of operator ergonomics, the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA) and European Union Directive 90/270/EEC and ISO 1503:2008 advise that an operator performing manual weight handling work should not deposit heavy weight below his hip, causing the robot to be designed with a height of $0.5 - 0.7\text{ m}$ to ensure safe manual transportation (Etxebarria, 2019). Similarly, to align with the dimensions of the Mediterranean greenhouse, where plants are placed in corridors with a width of 0.90 m to 1.10 m , the maximum

width of the robot is 0.6 m, adhering to the standard dimensions of a box of peppers. The resulting chassis must be adjusted to the dimensions of the greenhouse, taking into account the width of the aisles and the space required to change the corridors. Finally, considering that the transported boxes occupy a space of 0.8 m, and taking into account the sensors, it was decided that the robot should be 1 m long. In addition, this measurement allows the robot to rotate between corridors inside the greenhouse.

2.2. Sensors design specifications

In this section, an analysis of the specifications for the sensor subsystem will be performed, determining the placement of each element on the robot. It is important to note that this section details the physical location for each robot's component. To see the interaction at the software level, go to the section 5.2, where the algorithms used for each sensor and their interactions are detailed. More specifically refers to Fig. 22, special emphasis is placed on local robot communication.

In this case, ISO 26262-5:2018 determines the security conditions established from the hardware point of view.

An optical system capable of identifying objects and people in its surroundings must be installed to ensure optimal navigation for collaborative robotics. Based on local farmers' experience, objects that a robot can encounter in this agricultural environment typically have a size ranging from 20 to 120 cm in height, a factor that must be considered when designing the robot. Since image local interpretation involves a high computational cost, it is advisable to install an embedded system connected to the main computer to process the captured images of people, decoupling the recognition of the operator's pose from the navigation. In the latter case, the optimal height to identify the average stature of a person (1.8 m, as cited in (Spijker et al., 2008)) is calculated to be 1.65 m away. This is another crucial aspect to consider in vehicle design.

One of the most common sensors used for navigation is the LiDAR sensor. This element performs a 360 degree mapping of the environment, generating a 3D map for navigation and identifying items and people. These components typically have a vertical measurement range, which requires the sensor to be placed in a location accessible from obstacles throughout the horizontal plane to maximize its field of vision. To ensure safe autonomous navigation, the installation of ultrasonic sensors is very important (Mandow et al., 1996), achieving fault-tolerant redundancy that helps other sensors. This type of device uses high-frequency sound waves (ultrasonics) to detect the presence or distance of objects in their surroundings. These sensors must be installed around the robot's perimeter.

Finally, wheel speed sensors are one of the most essential components of the robot. It is responsible for providing real-time information about the robot's speed. Typically, you are expected to find them installed together with the motors in the same package, although at times it may be necessary to install them near the drive shaft.

2.3. Actuators design specifications

Initially, the different configurations and typical actuators used in today's literature are analyzed. The use of electric motors reduces the noise level and CO² emissions in an enclosed environment such as the greenhouse, making the work of the operators inside the greenhouse safer. In addition, it would allow the implementation of photovoltaic recharging systems, increasing the sustainability of greenhouse operations (Xie et al., 2022). However, in the experience of the authors in this field, the use of a *Ackerman* steering system reduces damage to the soil, especially during turns, compared to a differential steering system. In this respect, it has to be considered that most greenhouse floors are loose soils and that the vehicles used in the operations have to turn into very tight spaces. In this case, two motors are required: one will be responsible for traction, while the other will be responsible for steering the robot.

In this case, ISO 23482-2:2019 clarifies and provides guidance on new safety terms and requirements introduced to enable close human-robot interaction and human-robot contact in personal care robot applications, including mobile servant robots, physical assistant robots, and human-carrying robots. In the case of actuators, the interaction with the host computer will be explained in the section 5.1 as only physical considerations have been considered.

2.4. User interface design specifications

Another important aspect that requires specification is the user interface. In this case, mobile robots must comply with a series of regulations that, on the one hand, meet basic safety standards and, on the other hand, enable the machine to interact easily with the operator. This interface comprises software programming that will allow easy human-machine interaction and the programmer to access machine control. In addition to this characteristic, it is also important to ensure accessibility to safety hardware, which requires a control panel to ensure the integrity of the robot and the environment (Ahumada-Newhart and Olson, 2019).

On the one hand, the ISO 15066:2016 standard determines the necessity of implementing a device that emits a warning signal when the robot works in a collaborative environment with humans. In this case, the signal shall be both acoustic and visual, ensuring human-machine collaboration. This device will preferably be installed in the farmer's field of vision, displaying the necessary amount of information to guarantee the total integrity of the robot and the operator.

On the other hand, the ISO 13482:2014 standard obliges the designer to implement various manual physical mechanisms that determine safety during the robot's tasks. In this case, the robot must be connected manually, never automatically, to avoid unwanted behaviour. A manual control mechanism must be installed to allow the operator to control the robot's direction and speed. In addition, a safety button should be placed in the most accessible area possible so that the operator can stop the machine in an emergency.

3. Mechatronic design of the robot

This section describes the mechanical and electronic components chosen for the subsequent design of the robot. Typically, a robot's design follows a recursive approach to mechanical design by covering the actuator, sensor, and control subsystems. However, it has chosen to describe the actuators, sensors, and controller first and then the mechanical design to better understand the final prototype.

3.1. Electronic components

In the case of sensors, the robot will be fitted with the latest technology to self-locate, perceive the environment, and guarantee the safety of the operators when the robot is working next to them. It has been chosen:

- *Stereo camera Bumblebee BB2-08S2*¹: It has two lenses for capturing synchronized stereo images. It connects to the PC through a FireWire IEEE 1394 interface, providing a data transmission speed of 800 *Mb/s*. The stored data has a resolution of 1032 x 776 pixels. The field of view is 97° horizontally and 66° vertically within a range of 0.3 *m* to 20 *m*. Recording is done at 10 *Hz*, with a maximum frame rate of 20 fps and with a consumption of 1 *A* at 5 *V*. The camera is situated at the front to capture images suitable for identifying people and items or for guiding a robot through the corridors of the greenhouse.
- *Orbbec Persee +*²: The 3D camera possesses a sensing range from 0.6 to 8.0 *m* and functions effectively within temperatures ranging from 0° to 50°. This camera contains an embedded Linux or Android operating system on an Arch 64 processor capable of running complex systems inside. The Persee + model also provides connectivity options, including High Definition Multimedia Interface (HDMI), Bluetooth 5.0, and RJ45 Gigabit Ethernet with a consumption of 1.8 *A* at 5 *V*. This camera is intended to identify the pose of people as the robot works next to them, with the possibility of elaborating different collaboration strategies with humans in the future.
- *Ultrasonic kit Valeo*³: This kit contains twelve ultrasonic sensors, one Engine Control Unit (ECU), sensor holders, and one harness. The operating range is between 0.15 and 4.00 *m*, with a horizontal angle of 75° and 45° vertically via Controller Area Network (CAN) protocol. They operate between 11 and 16 *V* with a power consumption of 6 *W*. This sensor is intended to detect objects close to the robot's perimeter.
- *NOVATEL SPAN-IGM-A1*⁴: This GNSS offers a inertial navigation tightly coupled with an OEM615 receiver. It has a level accuracy of one meter to one centimeter, with operation between 10-30 *VDC* regulated with a power consumption of 0.87 *A*. It can be connected via serial, USB, CAN, and Multi I/O interface and is compatible with GPS, Globalnaya Navigatsionnaya Sputnikovaya Sistema (GNSS), Satellite Based Augmentation System (SBAS), and Real-Time Kinematic (RTK). In this case, this device will be used to obtain the positioning when the robot performs tasks outside the greenhouse between warehouses.
- *ANTCOM 42G1215X ARINC Antenna*⁵: This dual-band L1/L2 GPS antenna is connected to the Novatel SPAN-IGM-A1, with a power consumption of 1 *W*. The active configurations offer 2-stage integrated bandpass filtering

¹Bumblebee BB2-08S2 (website).

²Orbbec Persee + (website).

³Ultrasonic kit Valeo (website).

⁴NOVATEL SPAN-IGM-A1 (website)

⁵ANTCOM 42G1215X (website)

for high out-of-band rejection and limiter diodes to protect sensitive receiver electronics. Thanks to its high-frequency range, it can provide the triangulated position with nine satellites with an error of 50 *cm*. In this case, the antenna requires installation because it is expected that the robot will have to perform areas outside the greenhouse, which, being in the open, provides a correct location.

- *HISTTON PC*: Greenhouses frequently experience harsh environmental conditions characterized by high temperatures and humidity levels (Hernández et al., 2017). In light of these challenges, the platform is outfitted with a HISTTON computer featuring an Intel i7-8550U processor (4 *GHz*), an Intel UHD 620 graphics card with 24 Computers Unified Devices Architecture (CUDA) cores, and 32 GB of memory DDR4 Random Access Memory (RAM). This selection was made based on its ability to operate within a temperature range of 0 to 70 ° and a humidity range of 0 to 85 %. Consuming a mere 15 *W*, it demands minimal power, which is crucial to consider for battery capacity. Furthermore, the computer is configured with two disk partitions to accommodate both Ubuntu 20.04 with ROS Noetic and Ubuntu 22.04 with ROS 2 Humble, allowing users the flexibility to work with either version. It is important to note that this computer is equipped with a Wireless Fidelity (WIFI) network card whose wireless connection protocol is IEEE 802.11 ac (connections up to 1300 *Mbps*). This is ideal for establishing the pillars of cooperative robotics.
- *Elecrow 10.1*⁶: It is important that the robot has a device that is able to display the main characteristics of the sensors. For this design, the 10.1' Elecrow touch screen will be installed, which operates at 12 *V* and has a power consumption of 0.9 *A*. It has a HDMI connection. In addition, it has two 15 *W* loudspeakers that can emit sounds to alert the environment, which makes it a device that adapts to the specifications of the previous section.
- *Controller I24-70*⁷: For manual control, a mechanism that allows the robot to move forward or backward with a turn is added. To provide it with motion, a PG Drivers SK76977 (model I24 - 70) controller is installed, which changes the setpoint to the speed through a potentiometer and a joystick to set the advance or retardation. This reprogrammable DC controller can work with currents of up to 70 *A*. It has a battery and motor pin that can be controlled using a manual potentiometer. In this case, the manual operation mode will be determined as this article does not focus on the robot's control. On the other hand, the steering control is done by a second joystick, which drives the front motor in one direction or the other. In this case, the control is carried out by commutation thanks to two Schneider limit switches, which set the physical limits of rotation.

Finally, sensors have been installed to identify the pulse for future navigation. These elements are described in the following:

- *Encoder SICK DBS50E*⁸: This lap meter has a resolution of 1000 pulses per revolution, which provides high resolution. It is powered between 3.3 and 30 *V*, operates at up to 8000 *rpm*, and, in addition, has a zero-crossing sensor "Z" to mark one origin per turn. For the PC to be able to read the encoder, a Phidgets 1047 data acquisition card⁹ is installed, with a capacity of up to 4 encoders with reading of channels A, B and index.
- *Limit switch ZCP21*¹⁰: This identifier can cut off currents of around 10 *A* at 220 *V AC* at an activation speed of 0.01 *m/s*. This is installed to determine the maximum turning limit mentioned above.

In Fig. 1, one can see the schematic of the sensors with their physical means of connection.

3.2. Actuation and power components

In this section, the actuators and the power element shall be studied and selected, considering the considerations in Section 2.

- Motors

⁶Elecrow 10.1' (website)

⁷Controller I24-70 (website)

⁸SICK DBS50E (website).

⁹Phidgets 1047 (website).

¹⁰ZCP21 (website).

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Figure 1: Connection diagram of the electronic components

296 The robot must be able to move a 100 kg payload. In addition, the weight of the robot's mass for movement must
 297 be added. Taking into account the density of the S275J steel (material to be used for the construction), the estimated
 298 weight of the structure with all components will be 291 kg (data obtained from the 3D design of Section 3.4). If a
 299 safety factor of 1.5 (Kelly, 1996) is used, a final value of 378.3 kg is obtained. Considering that a speed of 0.5 m/s
 300 is required, it is possible to determine the power needed to move it. To carry out this calculation, the method developed
 301 in (Goris, 2005) has been followed through the Eq. 1 and 2 since it takes into account the mass itself, and the friction
 302 of the wheels on the ground as shown in the Fig 2.

Figure 2: Simple vehicle model (Goris, 2005)

$$F_{Pull} = F_{Weight} + F_{Friction}, \quad (1)$$

$$F_{Pull} = mg \sin(\alpha) + \mu mg \cos(\alpha), \quad (2)$$

303 where F_{Pull} is the force required to move a mass, F_{Weight} is the force of the robot's own weight (supposed with mass
 304 m), taking into account the friction force $F_{friction}$ on sandy soil (where μ is the rolling resistance coefficient with the
 305 ground, with a value of 0.5 according to (Irani et al., 2011)), F_N corresponding with the perpendicular component of
 306 the weight applied on the ramp, and with a slope of angle α to the horizontal (between 1 % and 2 % due to the typical
 307 characteristics of a Mediterranean type greenhouse). The power needed to drive the robot responds to the Eq. 3.

$$P_{max_T} = F_{pull} \cdot v_{max}, \quad (3)$$

where v_{max} is the maximum speed, equal to 0.5 m/s as was previously commented. In this case, the traction motor must have a power greater than 463.84 W , so a 500 W and 24 V ECM350/030¹¹ motor is chosen. This motor is ideal for use in greenhouses. It has IP66 protection, so it will not be damaged by humidity and dust, and an H23 stop brake, which increases its safety for working with humans. It will stop if it suffers a power cut.

On the other hand, the steering motor requires the pivoting momentum between the ground and the wheels, commonly called "Torque" or " $M_{steering}$." In this case, the method followed in (Gabriel et al., 2011) has been used in Eq. 5, which takes into account the friction of the tire with the ground, as shown in Eq. 4.

$$M_{steering} = F_{weight} \cdot \rho_p, \quad (4)$$

$$P_{max_S} = M_{steering} \cdot \omega_{max}, \quad (5)$$

where ρ_p is the friction coefficient of wheels and ω_{max} is the maximum angular velocity measured through the encoder. In this case, a power of 73.18 W is required so, that a CM100/040¹² motor of 140 W and 24 V is chosen. In this case, this motor is also ideal for use in greenhouses. As was previously commented, it has IP66 protection and an H23 stop brake.

• Bearing

Once the power generated by the motor has been determined, the next step is to carefully select the bearings. Of all the bearings in the robot, the most critical is the one in the plane parallel to the ground, which carries all the weight. A double-row angular contact needle roller bearing, capable of supporting high axial forces (more compact axial profile), is usually used for this type of application. However, it risks breaking when the bearing cannot handle the axial load. To solve this problem, two similar bearings were used for all four wheels, replacing them with a double-row angular contact ball bearing. The capacities of this bearing are significantly high, although it was chosen mainly because of the space restrictions imposed by the inner diameter.

In this case, the bearing chosen is the model 51412 M from the SKF catalogue (SKF, 2015). This bearing has a working load of up to 7.7 kN , supporting twice the weight for which the robot is designed. Moreover, as it is a pure axial load bearing, the robot gains stability on sandy ground, which, together with its robustness, allows it to withstand the irregular and sandy soil typical of greenhouses. In addition, this bearing requires lubrication with high-viscosity lubricants, which results in a maintenance requirement of once every six months. Finally, it is equipped with seals to retain the grease necessary for smooth rotational movement. Its service life is also remarkably long and can be calculated using specific formulae in (Popescu et al., 2018), assuming that the bearing operates statically.

• Wheels

The robot will move mainly inside the greenhouse, and the ground in Mediterranean greenhouses is typically sandy and uneven. Therefore, wheels that can move without displacing soil, turn with minimal soil disturbance, and maintain vehicle stability will be selected. In this case, as the width of the corridor through which the robot must travel is 2 m and the objective is to maximize the support section between the wheels and the floor, a model with a diameter of 20 cm and a rolling width of 30 cm is chosen, guaranteeing a correct distribution of the weight. The tire is chosen from a local company, whose main characteristics are centered on the weight it can withstand, which is 120 kg per wheel (480 kg in total).

• Batteries

Once the power consumed by the motors and sensors is known, the next step is the selection of the batteries, which play a crucial role in a robot because the more significant the capacity, the greater the autonomy. The motors chosen will operate at 24 V DC, which determines the voltage at which the batteries must operate. The reference value takes into account the current consumed by the set of actuators and sensors, which is 26.6 A for the motors and 8.1 A for the

¹¹ECM350/030 (website).

¹²CM100/040 (website).

347 sensors. Another critical aspect determining the battery's choice is the desired autonomy, as the robot must be capable
 348 of enduring an entire workday of harvesting use. Considering that a farmer works for 8 hours during the harvest season,
 349 the robot should not require charging during that period, and it does not constantly operate at maximum power. An
 350 autonomy of at least 4 hours is considered (Crespo et al., 2017). It is possible to determine the correct battery capacity
 351 using Ohm's Law from Eq. (6).

$$I = \frac{P}{V}, \quad (6)$$

352 where V is voltage in Volts, P is the power consumed, and I is current in amps. Shows the total current required to
 353 determine the autonomy for the propulsion and steering motor in Eq. 7.

$$I = I_T + I_S. \quad (7)$$

354 Obtaining a result of 26.67 A when the robot advances at maximum speed. Considering the consumption of sensors
 355 and considering that an autonomy of 4 hours, a battery of at least 136.8 Ah will be required. The NBA 4TG 12 NH
 356 ¹³, capable of providing up to 157 Ah at 12 V voltage, was the battery chosen. Measurement of 345x170x285 cm in
 357 dimensions and weighting 37kg. Therefore, two batteries will be installed in series, obtaining the necessary voltage
 358 for the motors and, using a 24-12 V converter RSD-100D-12 ¹⁴, for the voltage for the sensors.

359 In order to reduce human workload, the WIBOTIC ¹⁵ wireless charging station has been installed to allow the robot
 360 to charge autonomously when needed. In this case, the robot is fitted with the RC-100-WP receiver which, together
 361 with the OC-262-WP on-board charger, allows a 300 W inductive charging flow, achieving a full charge in a total of
 362 13 hours. Fig. 3 shows an electrical diagram of the operation of all sensors, as well as their connection to the power
 363 supply.

Figure 3: Electric connection diagram

364 3.3. Mechanical design

365 Once sensors, actuators, and power supply have been chosen, and without losing sight of the general considerations,
 366 the next step is to make the 3D model for the robot, from which the plans for its construction will be extracted. For

¹³NBA 4TG12NH: (website).

¹⁴RSD-100D-12 (website).

¹⁵WIBOTIC: (website).

367 the design, the CAE software SolidWorks Simulation® has been selected. SolidWorks is the leading CAD software
 368 for mechanical design, boasting a user-friendly graphical interface (SolidWorks, 2005).

369 One of the most important aspects to take into account before starting the robot design is the weight and dimensions
 370 of the batteries (37 kg and 345x170x285 cm, respectively). They will be placed in the center of the robot and as close
 371 to the ground as possible, achieving a lower center of gravity and even weight distribution on all four wheels. The
 372 compartments will be prepared to house all electronics, characterizing the rest of the components with a rectangular
 373 profile of X40 (AENOR, 2011). Fig. 4 shows a view of the complete result.

Figure 4: Robotic chassis

374 The method of transmitting the movement of the motors to the different axles will be by chains, given their
 375 robustness (Rodrigues, 2018). In the case of the rear transmission, as can be seen in Fig. 5, two straight pinions are
 376 installed, seeking a transmission ratio between the traction motor and the ground so that the robot reaches a maximum
 377 of 0.5 m/s, as specified in the general specifications. Therefore, the driving pinion will have twenty teeth and the driven
 378 pinion forty, obtaining a transmission ratio of 0.000675, taking into account the reduction of the worm gear-crown of
 379 the motor itself.

Figure 5: Rear transmissions

380 In the case of the front transmission, no reduction gear will be installed, as it is considered that the rotational speed
 381 itself is sufficient to navigate the greenhouse. In Fig. 6, a 20-tooth sprocket is installed to change the transmission plane
 382 and is connected to both forks using a chain.

383 To ensure that ultrasonics can detect the environment, a front and rear bumper shall be designed to allow the robot
 384 to have a full view, achieved by a 45° chamfer horizontally. Based on this design, the dead spots of the robot should be
 385 adjusted to allow it to stop when approaching within 20 cm of the robot direction, according to ISO 18497:2018 and
 386 as shown in Fig. 7.

387 The manual control panel will be placed on the rear bumper as, according to the ISO 18497:2018 standard, the
 388 robot must be manually connected, eliminating the possibility of remote activation. Installing an emergency stop button
 389 is mandatory to allow manual shutdown when the user needs it. Fig. 8 shows the result of this design.

Figure 6: Front transmissions

Figure 7: Robot dead spots (dimensions in centimetres (*cm*))

Figure 8: Bumper

390 Transport module is proposed for use inside the greenhouse. This is designed without sharp or potentially harmful
 391 terminal components that could injure the operator. Additionally, it provides an ample transport area capable of
 392 accommodating two standardized local vegetable crates. The design result is presented in Fig. 9a. The joining
 393 mechanism can be observed in Fig. 9b. Thanks to a rectangular X60 profile, it can slide and be replaced by another
 394 module, enhancing the robot's versatility and the potential for designing various agricultural implements.

Figure 9: Transport module

395 Lastly, considering that some components must be positioned above the robot's base, it is necessary to design an
 396 element that remains fixed to the chassis and meets the desired height. In this case, a mast is chosen to be installed at

Table 1
Description of the elements

Element	Description	Element	Description	Element	Description
1	Porticoes	10	ECM350/030	19	Left fork
2	Display board 1	11	Protection plate right	20	Left bearing
3	Moving part of the mast	12	Rear right wheel	21	ECM100/040
4	Load support table	13	Front right wheel	22	Front bumper
5	Transport element	14	Right bushing	23	Front left wheel
6	ON/OFF button	15	Driving axle	24	Right bushing
7	Fixed part of mast	16	Right bearing	25	Right protection plate
8	Emergency shutdown	17	NBA 4TG 12 NH	26	Rear right wheel
9	Rear bumper	18	Right fork	27	Chassis

397 an altitude of 1,5 m, allowing the placement of the camera for human identification, LiDAR, and GPS (see Fig. 10).
 398 This multilevel mast gives the robot additional capabilities and the possibility to study the interpretation of various
 399 sensors at different heights, estimating the most optimal one. Two X30 telescopic profiles are used. At the top, two
 400 platforms are installed: the first houses the LiDAR, and the second houses the GPS to capture most of the sky. Since
 401 the LiDAR requires 360-degree vision, the identification camera will also be installed on the upper platform. Finally,
 402 two plates are installed where the screens will be, one at the rear, where the supervision interface will be established,
 403 and the other at the front, where the interaction interface with the farmer will be designed, facilitating the collaboration
 404 between the machine and the operator.

Figure 10: Masthead

3.4. Assembling of 3D model

To achieve this design, 491 components have been assembled, including screws, components, axes, and the main structure. The resulting 3D model of the robot is shown in Fig. 11.

The *Ackermann* configuration is distinguished by two front forks that define the robot's direction. In addition, side projection covers are installed, where the logos of the spindle protector will be placed. In the interior, all control units are placed. An exploded view of the resulting assembly is shown in Fig. 12, the description and location of which can be found in the Tab. 1.

All parts were connected with bolt patterns, the sheets were made by the operation corresponding to 3 mm thick metal sheets, and the elements were simulated to be spot welded. The result of the assembly was a success as it met all the requirements and exceeded the expectations. The stability result meets the minimum requirements, so the design

Figure 11: 3D model robot

Figure 12: 3D robot model - exploded view

415 results indicate that the prototype can be realised. Finally, the most important physical properties (density, elastic
416 modulus, etc.) are shown in the Tab. 2.

417 **4. Test facilities**

418 The experiments were carried out at the Agroconnect facilities in the Municipal District of La Cañada de San
419 Urbano, Almería. These facilities received co-funding from the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities in

Table 2
Physical properties

Mass	291.38 [Kg]
Volume	1.22 [m^3]
Area of surface	0.953 [m^2]
Centre of mass	(-0.112, -0.259, -0.023) [m^2]

420 collaboration with the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER) as part of the grant program to acquire cutting-
421 edge scientific and technological equipment in 2019. The location is at coordinates 36°50' N and 2°24' W, with an
422 elevation of 3 m above sea level and a terrain slope of 1% in the North direction (refer to Fig. 13).

(a) Greenhouse outdoor

(b) Greenhouse indoor

Figure 13: Agroconnect greenhouse

423 This kind of greenhouse is characterised by a plastic cover and no climatic actuators such as heating, used only in
424 critical events. They are multi-span greenhouses with a structure made of wood or galvanised steel. The average surface
425 is around 1 ha, with spans of different sizes from 4 to 9 m, and even more, maximum height ranges from low greenhouses
426 of just over 3 to 6-8 m. A central corridor, 2 m wide, serves as the main thoroughfare, branching into eleven aisles on
427 each side. The North-side aisles measure 2 m wide and 12.5 m long, while those on the South side span 2 m wide and
428 22.5 m long. Radiating from the central aisle are narrower secondary corridor, each just one meter wide, facilitating
429 the movement of mobile robotic units. The diverse array of robotic units operating within these facilities, including
430 the mobile robots from the AGRICOBOT¹⁶ and AGRICOBOT II¹⁷ projects and maintenance drones, seamlessly
431 integrates into this overarching architecture. These units operate with their fog-based systems, enabling them to access
432 and contribute valuable information to and from the broader spectrum of systems in operation.

433 The crop usually grows in soil culture; it is the majority compared to soilless crops such as hydroponics. The most
434 common form of cultivation is a soil modification called "sanding", which consists of placing different layers of soil
435 on top of the original soil, which tends to be very clayey, or in other words, impermeable. The three layers usually used
436 are: a layer of sand in the lower zone on top of the original soil, then a layer of manure, and finally a sandy layer that
437 helps water droplets penetrate quickly and homogeneously to reduce evapotranspiration. Plants are placed in corridors
438 with a width of 0.9 m to 1.10 m with two aims: to promote natural ventilation and facilitate labour for workers and

¹⁶Project identifier: UAL2020-TEP-A1991 (UAL/CTEICU/FEDER)

¹⁷Project identifier: PY20_00767 (CTEICU/FEDER).

439 machines. Greenhouses are used mainly for the production of vegetables, followed by ornamental plants. The main
 440 products are tomatoes, peppers, melons, watermelons, zucchini, eggplants, and strawberries.

441 It usually does not increase further due the effects of strong winds. The main actuator is the natural ventilation
 442 used to reduce the temperature and the humidity content. Oriented in an East-West ridge configuration, the design
 443 maximizes natural ventilation from the prevailing winds in the region. To ensure comprehensive monitoring of critical
 444 variables within the system and capture real-time meteorological conditions, both inside and outside the greenhouse,
 445 six interior IoT (Internet of Things, integrated into a larger cloud-based framework (Muñoz et al., 2022)) stations
 446 have been strategically positioned. These stations can measure various parameters, including temperature, relative
 447 humidity, ambient pressure, leaf humidity, solar radiation, PAR radiation, and CO₂ concentration. Additionally, they
 448 can offer information on soil-related metrics such as volumetric content, electrical conductivity, and soil temperature.
 449 Furthermore, the infrastructure incorporates two external meteorological stations that track external variables such as
 450 precipitation, wind speed and direction, radiation levels, temperature, humidity and CO₂ concentration (Moreno Úbeda
 451 et al., 2022).

452 5. Robot operation validation

453 This section shows the validation results of the robot operation, verifying that the specifications in Section 2 have
 454 been met. Once the 3D model was completed, the initial prototype was built, it was reprofiled and machined again to
 455 refine all the crucial aspects, thus completing the prototype of the AGRICOBOT II robot (see Fig. 14).

Figure 14: AGRICOBOT II Robot

456 As can be seen, the real design complies with the specifications designed in the 3D model. The sensors comply
 457 with all the restrictions imposed in the design, resulting in a safe and robust robot that complies with all the regulations
 458 mentioned in Section 2.

459 5.1. Actuation subsystem validation

460 The motors must then be validated for the correct operation by verifying that the manual control system works
 461 correctly. For this purpose, two tests were performed inside the greenhouse, a speed test of the traction motor and a

462 steering test of the steering motor. From these tests, the dynamic operating behavior and the dead-zone of the engines
 463 were obtained.

464 5.1.1. Traction motor

465 The I24-70 controller has different pins organized in two ports: pins 6, 7, and 8 to be connected to a potentiometer
 466 for velocity, and pins 12, 13, 14, and 15 to set the direction (forward or backward). In this way, a two-position joystick
 467 is used to control the direction of motor rotation and a potentiometer to adjust the speed. In order to determine the
 468 speed profile of the robot, a train of positive and negative steps is set up out of the dead-zone of the motor.

469 Due to the friction force between components of the same shaft and between the output gears of the same shaft, a
 470 minimum intensity of electromotive force is needed to overcome these forces and cause a rotation, so it establishes a
 471 minimum voltage level for the coils so that the robot can move forward and overcome this minimum electromotive force.
 472 This phenomenon is traditionally called "Dead-Zone" and is found in all motorized elements. In order to characterise
 473 this phenomenon, a ramped input is provided, observing the behavior of the output to determine the limits of the
 474 dead-zone of the motor. The result of this test is shown in Fig. 15, where the output is given by the estimated velocity
 475 of the robot from the motor encoder.

Figure 15: Dead-Zone response and limited saturation response of traction motor

476 Under the given circumstances, it is exposed to an equivalent voltage ranging between -22.9 V and 23.1 V . The
 477 result is a dead zone between -1.73 and 1.5 V .

478 Now, in order to characterise the dynamic behaviour of the motor out of its dead-zone, a train of steps is applied
 479 to the motor input, and pulses provided by the encoder are multiplied by the transmission ratio of the motor to obtain
 480 the estimated velocity of the robot, giving the response profile obtained in Fig. 16. In order to minimise the effect of
 481 the localised noise in the encoder itself, a low-pass filter with a time constant of 100 seconds is applied (Åström and
 482 Murray, 2021).

Figure 16: Raw data from forward open loop test of traction motor

483 As can be seen, the robot responded perfectly to a change of input to the robot, validating the correct operation of
 484 both the motor and the encoder, providing the opportunity for future work to be carried out, and implementing different
 485 control techniques.

486 5.1.2. Steering motor

487 In the case of the steering motor, the same test is repeated both for the dead zone and the saturation limits and to
 488 validate the correct operation of the robot. Fig. 17 shows the result of the test for the dead zone, and Fig. 18 shows
 489 the angular velocity measured with the encoder with the same filter and orientation of the robot calculated integrating
 490 from this velocity (Corke and Khatib, 2011).

Figure 17: Dead-Zone response and limited saturation response of steering motor

Figure 18: Raw data from clockwise direction open loop test of steering motor

491 As can be seen, the steering motor has a range of (-23.5 and -0.89) V in the reverse direction and (1.11 and
 492 23.4) V in the clockwise direction. The tests validate the correct functioning of the robot steering. These results
 493 lay the foundations for future implementation of low-level control algorithms, from Proportional, Integrative, and
 494 Derivative (PID) controllers (Cañadas-Aránega et al., 2024), to advanced control techniques, providing the opportunity
 495 to implement them in robot simulators (Blanco-Claraco et al., 2023) for later implementation in the real robot.

496 5.1.3. Validation of the manoeuvrability of the robot

497 The main skill that the robot must have is the navigation in the greenhouse. For this, it must be verified that the
 498 prototype can navigate through the greenhouse with a load of 100 kg at 0.5m/s. With the weight well distributed and
 499 secured, the robot is manually guided into a greenhouse corridor, providing maximum tension and directly measuring
 500 the speed by the encoder. When it reaches the aisle transfer point, the robot turns to the next aisle, thus validating

501 that the prototype can navigate through an aisle in a straight line without problems and that it can turn around with its
 502 maximum turning radius. The operator guided this test using the control panel, storing the trajectory in Fig. 19b, with
 503 an average speed estimated from the odometry in Fig. 19a.

Figure 19: Validation of the manoeuvrability of the robot

504 As observed, the robot can follow a typical zigzag trajectory inside a Mediterranean greenhouse, fulfilling the
 505 design specifications. Fig. 20 shows an image of the real robot inside the greenhouse, moving from aisle to aisle and
 506 verifying its manoeuvrability.

Figure 20: AGRICOBIOT II making a turn in the shuttle between corridors in the greenhouse

507 5.2. Perception subsystems validation

508 In this section, the sensors performance is evaluated when the robot works alongside operators, analysing and
 509 interpreting their suitability for enabling autonomous navigation. The robot uses the ROS (Macenski et al., 2022a) to
 510 manage the information provided by the sensors. In particular, it uses ROS 2. ROS represents a set of software libraries
 511 and tools designed to facilitate the development of robot applications. From drivers to cutting-edge algorithms and with
 512 powerful developer tools, ROS provides everything you need for the development of a robotics project (Macenski et al.,
 513 2022b). In addition, all software is available as open source (Meeussen et al., 2010). The Mobile Robot Programming
 514 Toolkit (MRPT) library (Blanco-Claraco et al., 2024) was installed to manage the data from most of the sensors. In
 515 addition, the OpenCV 4.2.0 vision library (Bradski and Kaehler, 2008) was also used for vision-related tasks and
 516 algorithms that focus on SLAM.

Specifically, for Velodyne VLP16 `mola_lidar_odometry` from the MOLA framework (Blanco-Claraco, 2019) was employed, ORB_SLAM3 to SLAM for Bumblebee (Mur-Artal and Tardós, 2017), the library MoveNet that has been developed in (Jo and Kim, 2022) for Persee +, and the application provided by the Valeo company `uls_link` for ultrasonic Valeo. The origin is defined at the `base_link` (positioned in the middle of the robot's rear axle), from which the other sensor poses are defined.

- Stereo and RGBD camera: $x = \text{right}$, $y = \text{down}$, $z = \text{forward}$.
- LIDAR: $x = \text{forward}$, $y = \text{left}$, $z = \text{up}$.
- Ultrasonic: Each sensor is reference in `base_link`.

Fig. 21 shows the perception subsystem, equipped with a Bumblebee stereo camera, Velodyne VLP16 3D LiDAR, Orbbec Persee +, and Valeo ultrasonic, with the corresponding reference systems.

Figure 21: Perception subsystem mounted on the robot. The x -axis is represented in red, the y -axis in green, and the z -axis in blue

These sensors are connected using the diagram in Fig. 22, which details the software connection in ROS and the purpose of each one for the tests carried out in the real greenhouse.

5.2.1. Obstacles map from the Ultrasonic sensors

Ultrasonics were installed on the prototype and tested using the tools provided by the provider, Valeo. In this case, the SDKs are provided on a USB stick to work on ROS Noetic or ROS 2 Foxy, together with an application called `uls_link`. This application can be installed on both Linux and Windows, providing the opportunity to perform the first tests efficiently. The calibration is done in the application itself, starting a guided process that calibrates each ultrasound's maximum and minimum ranges.

To validate the installation of these sensors, the robot was placed in front of the operator, standing between the aisles of the greenhouse, and the farmer slowly approaching the front sensors. The result of the test is shown in Fig. 23.

As can be seen, the robot's ultrasonics identify obstacles at the sides due to the tomato row plants themselves and at the front due to the farmer. In this case, when approaching slowly, the obstacle map was checked and the distance designed in Fig. 7 was validated, determining the magnificent behaviour of the sensor.

5.2.2. SLAM with Bumblebee

ORB_SLAM3 is the first real-time SLAM library able to perform Visual, Visual-Inertial, and Multi-Map SLAM with monocular, stereo, and RGB-D cameras, using pinhole and fisheye lens models. In all sensor configurations, ORB_SLAM3 is as robust as the best systems available in the literature and significantly more accurate (Campos et al., 2021). The correct validation of the functioning of the cameras plays a fundamental role in collaborative robotics with

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Figure 22: ROS connection diagram

Figure 23: Valeo obstacle map test

546 humans and cooperative robotics with other robots as it provides the robot with essential characteristics for navigation
 547 and joint work. In addition, the large number of objects and the movement of operators within a greenhouse make it
 548 difficult to use traditional algorithms in ideal environments, which is a unique challenge today. For this reason, this
 549 article shows the design of a robot with sensors installed for immediate use of the most commonly used technologies,
 550 validating their correct functioning for future autonomous navigation. In this case, the robot aims to identify the farmer
 551 in the tasks to be carried out, ensuring collaboration and interaction between the human and the machine.

552 • Bumblebee calibration

553 The intrinsic parameters of the stereo camera were determined using the `kinect-stereo-calib` application from
 554 the Mobile Robot Programming Toolkit (MRPT) (Blanco-Claraco et al., 2024). These parameters include the focal
 555 lengths (f_x, f_y) , optical centers (c_x, c_y) , pin-hole distortion parameters (k_1, k_2, p_1, p_2) , and the left-to-right relative
 556 pose. Extrinsic parameters specify the relative poses of different sensor frames of reference. In this case, the same
 557 method has been followed as in (Cañadas-Aránega et al., 2024) since it is the same camera for the same purpose.

(a) Left raw image

(b) Right raw image

Figure 24: Stereo image of Bumblebee

558 • SLAM Bumblebee test

559 The test was carried out by placing the robot next to the farmer as he picked fruit at different heights in the crop
 560 during the harvesting season. The stereo camera has two lenses (Fig. 24a and 24b) showing how the operator performs
 561 a harvesting task. The results are shown in Fig. 25.

Figure 25: SLAM of Bumblebee next to farmer with ORB-SLAM3

562 It can be seen how the mapping has identified the operator, validating the correct functioning of the camera intended
 563 for obstacle detection in navigation.

564 5.2.3. SLAM with Velodyne VLP16

565 With the same test performed with the camera, the robot design will be validated with the Velodyne VLP16. The
 566 LiDAR was calibrated according to (Geiger et al., 2013), guaranteeing the quality of the data. The human moves
 567 slightly forward, and the robot observes him, obtaining a point cloud in real time. The result of the mapping obtained
 568 is shown in Fig. 26a, showing a frame obtained from the recorded data set (Cañadas-Aránega, 2024).

569 • LiDAR calibration

570 To perform the Velodyne VLP16 LiDAR calibration, the steps described in (Geiger et al., 2012b) were followed,
 571 optimising the error in the Euclidean distance of 50 manually selected correspondences and a robust measure on the
 572 disparity error with respect to the three top performing stereo methods in the KITTI stereo benchmark (Geiger et al.,
 573 2012a).

574

- **SLAM LiDAR test**

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Figs. 26a and 26b show the result of performing SLAM with MOLA while the farmer performs the harvesting task.

(a) SLAM of Velodyne VLP16 without farmer

(b) SLAM of Velodyne VLP16 next to farmer

Figure 26: SLAM Velodyne test with a jet type colour intensity

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In addition, the mapping identifies the surrounding plants, allowing navigation through the greenhouse (Cañadas-Aránega et al., 2024). Furthermore, there is a clear difference between a greenhouse corridor with and without a farmer. In this case, it can be seen how the LiDAR perfectly captures the farmer, allowing the implementation of collaborative strategies in the future.

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5.2.4. Pose detection with Orbbec Persee +

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The MoveNet library is designed to process raw camera images and convert them into valuable inputs for vision algorithms: rectified mono/color images, stereo disparity images, and stereo point clouds. In this case, on the basis of (Feng et al., 2022), where the authors use a binocular camera, it is possible to determine the pose of a human. This library can be installed on the camera's own Ubuntu 18.04 operating system, allowing it to work on its own and freeing the main computer from the burden of image reconstruction. As was previously commented, in the greenhouse scenario, farmer recognition is fundamental in establishing correct communication between humans and robots. Therefore, along the same lines as the previous validations, the same test will be carried out to ensure correct operation.

589

- **Presee + calibration**

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592

For the calibration of this camera, the library itself provides a tool called `camera_calibration` that calibrates monocular and stereo cameras in the ROS system. The Camera Info page provides a detailed description of the parameters used by the Movenet.

593

- **Pose detection Persee + test**

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Repeating the same experiment, Fig. 27 shows the result of farmer identification.

In this case, we can see how it draws an image perfectly positioned with the operator, providing an excellent opportunity to implement more advanced collaborative robotics algorithms in the future.

597

6. Conclusions

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This paper presents the development of a novel *Ackermann*-type collaborative mobile agricultural robot to provide transport work inside greenhouses together with farmers. Furthermore, the robot is equipped with enough technology to establish an internet connection, thus entering the new era of Industry 4.0 with the Internet of Things (IoT) and laying the first foundations for cooperation with other agricultural machinery. The article explains the process from

Figure 27: Pose detection farmer inside greenhouse

602 the first idea-driven brush strokes to validating all mobile robotics sensors for collaborating next to the operator. The
 603 results meet the expectations of the development itself, as well as being able to perform tests on the prototype with real
 604 farmers in the area. Continuous improvement of this type of agricultural robot is crucial to promote research in such
 605 a complicated environment as a greenhouse, specially in Mediterranean greenhouses, where there is still much to be
 606 perfected.

607 At present, there is no prototype capable of carrying such a large payload through the greenhouse and of navigating
 608 in such a complex environment without being a problem for the environment. This design allows the community of
 609 researchers to test the most commonly used algorithms to perform tasks such as SLAM, people detection, obstacle
 610 mapping, etc., in a unique agricultural environment focused on intensive agriculture under greenhouses. Mapping,
 611 orientation, and precise navigation are crucial for various robotic activities within greenhouses, particularly on the
 612 transport task.

613 This novel design is intended to usher in a new generation of agricultural robots, laying the mechanical foundations
 614 for moving smoothly through a typical Mediterranean greenhouse and the foundations for the hardware needed to make
 615 collaborative journeys with agriculture at the height of the vegetable harvesting season. However, this prototype will
 616 continue to improve as this article is only the first step to being able to carry out various tasks inside the greenhouse,
 617 from the systematic comparison of the autonomous navigation of this *Ackermann* robot and a differential robot working
 618 cooperatively to the monitoring of the state of the crop, growth or pest detection thanks to the sensors installed and
 619 validated in this work.

620 The next step will be the implementation in ROS 2 Humble of different control techniques that allow us to trace and
 621 determine the speed and direction of the robot itself between a displacement between an origin and an end. Currently,
 622 the robot has the necessary technology to establish a closed loop by implementing different control techniques, from the
 623 odometry captured by the encoders to navigation algorithms based on the orientation provided by the LiDAR sensors
 624 or stereo cameras. In addition, the vision system provides the opportunity to implement pest identification algorithms,
 625 adaptation to different types of terrain, and mathematical models of plant growth, among others.

626 This paper aims to present and share the development of how to implement an agricultural robot in a complicated
 627 environment. As already mentioned, some robots navigate inside greenhouses. However, they need to have the capacity
 628 to carry a large payload, establish collaborative work with humans, and have the basic technology to connect to the
 629 internet to manage and monitor the different variables of the environment. The validation of all the sensors provides
 630 solid support to the most important objectives of this project, offering an apparent reference for researchers to use as
 631 a starting point for improving their agricultural machines and navigation algorithms.

632 CRediT authorship contribution statement

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641 Declaration of competing interest

642 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have
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644 Data availability

645 No data was used for the research described in the article.

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